

Lowland rice field weeds in Nueva Ecija, Philippines

P. P. Pablico, research assistant, and K. Moody, agronomist, Agronomy Department, IRRI

We surveyed rice field weeds in barangays Malimba, Mangino, Santa Cruz, and Santo Cristo Norte of Gapan, Nueva Ecija, in Feb 1984. Seventy-eight randomly selected fields were visited during heading to flowering after weed control; 66 were wet seeded (pregerminated seed sown on puddled soil) and 12 were transplanted. The percentage cover was determined visually for all weed species.

Twenty-six weed species of 21 genera and 13 families were identified (see table). Fifty percent of the weed species belonged to Poaceae and Cyperaceae. Seventeen species were found in transplanted rice and 25 in wet seeded rice; 16 were common to both cultures. *Echinochloa colona* was the only species in transplanted rice that was not found in wet seeded rice.

E. glabrescens was observed in all the fields surveyed. *Monochoria vaginalis* occurred in 77% of the fields, *Fimbristylis miliacea* in 59%, and *Paspalum distichum* in 58%. For three of these species, infestation was greater

Percentage of fields^a infested with weeds and the severity of infestation in transplanted and wet seeded rice in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Transplanted (12)		Wet seeded (66)	
		Fields infested (%)	Cover (%)	Fields infested (%)	Cover (%)
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	100	9	100	21
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	92	7	74	12
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> L.	Cyperaceae	50	8	61	18
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	50	7	59	6
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	8	45	56	21
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	50	1	39	2
<i>Lindernia anagallis</i> (Burm. f.) Pinnell	Scrophulariaceae	25	39	42	12
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	Asteraceae	33	<1	24	7
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	17	3	30	3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	17	<1	26	14
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Marsileaceae	33	18	21	22
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	33	11	21	4
<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	Rubiaceae	17	21	21	10
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	Sphenocleaceae	8	<1	18	1
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	—	—	14	4
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	—	—	9	6
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forsk	Convolvulaceae	8	<1	6	<1
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	8	15	6	<1
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms	Pontederiaceae	—	—	8	2
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	25	10	—	—
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	Poaceae	—	—	5	<1
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) Dc.	Amaranthaceae	—	—	3	17
<i>Sphaeranthus africanus</i> L.	Asteraceae	—	—	3	<1
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	Commelinaceae	—	—	3	<1
<i>Fimbristylis acuminata</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	—	—	2	<1
<i>Fuirena ciliaris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Cyperaceae	—	—	2	<1

^a Number of fields surveyed is in parentheses.

in wet seeded than in transplanted rice.

In addition to weed species that commonly occur in wet seeded and transplanted rice, we identified the

following potential problem weeds:

Scirpus supinus, *Lindernia anagallis*, and *Marsilea minuta*. *♂*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Bird damage to rice in Visveswaraiah Canal Tract (VCT)

A. K. Chakravarthy and Gubbaiah, Regional Research Station, Mudigere and Mandya, Karnataka, India

Birds *Ploceus philippinus* L. (baya weaver bird), *P. manyar* Horsfield (streaked weaver bird), *Lonchura striata* L. (whitebacked munia), *L. malacca* L. (black-headed munia), *L. punctulata* L. (spotted munia), and *Estrilda amandava* L. (red munia) feed on rice grains in VCT, Mandya. We recorded bird

Table 1. Feeding rate, flock size, and abundance of rice birds, VCT, Mandya,^a India.

Bird	Feeding rate (pecks/min) ($\bar{x} \pm SD$)	Flock size (max - min)	Population (%)	Habitat preference
Streaked weaver bird	8.2 ± 2.4	46-15	69	Wet
Baya weaver bud	6.0 ± 0.9	17-4	8	Wet
Blackheaded munia	6.0 ± 1.7	33-14	19	Wet
Whitebacked munia	3.0 ± 1.0	3-2	<1	Dry
Spotted munia	2.5 ± 1.2	5-2	<1	Dry
Red munia	3.6 ± 0.8	9-3	3	Wet
CD at 5% by 'F' test	ns	ns	18	—

^a Numbers in a column are ± of 15 observations recorded from fields adjacent to patches of marsh and sugarcane.

populations, feeding rate, and habitat preference in rice fields in May-Jun 1985

and calculated the relative economic importance of each species.